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The Effects of Peer Influence on Students' Motivation

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Abstract

This study determined the effects of peer influence on students' motivation among high school students in Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. in Governor Generoso, Davao Oriental, Philippines. Using stratified random sampling, this study employed a sample of 172 high school students from the total population. Data was collected through a modified survey questionnaire. Results reveal very high levels of peer influence which yielded a mean of 4.23 and students' motivation of 4.30. Furthermore, regression was used to test the influence of peer influence to students' motivation which yielded an f -value of 0.00. This result reveals that peer influence significantly affects motivation of students in MSSSI. Furthermore, this study concludes a notion that any adjustment made on peer influence has a positive or negative effect to students' motivation. This simply implies that peers have effects to the students' motivation in learning and interaction in school. Moreover, this study recommends improving peer influence positively because this would positively affect students' enthusiasm toward development. Thus, it is essential to strengthen and enhance the implementation of Peer Club and its relevant activities in schools most especially in MSSSI.

Keywords: *peer influence, students' motivation, effects, quantitative*

Introduction

In learning, motivation is important and has different sides to it. People define it in different ways. Motivation means you are mentally and emotionally ready to do something, and you decide to keep trying to reach a specific goal. Being active in class is important for students to learn and get better. When students join in, they can learn more, show they understand the lessons, feel more sure of themselves, and use what they've learned (Acedillo & Saro, 2023).

Many students rely on their peers to help them grow and mature emotionally. Having good friends allows for social compassion, influencing how students see themselves. This statement emphasizes how important peer groups are in almost every aspect of a teenager's development. It affects their social and emotional lives, and even how they approach school. By paying attention to these aspects, we can see that they impact students' academic performance (Filade et al., 2019).

In schools, peers have always had an impact. Studies show that people form groups to help and guide each other. Teenagers, especially students, often hang out with friends who are similar to them in behavior, likes, and attitudes. This includes things like school goals, music taste, political views, fashion, or favorite activities. Peer pressure is when friends try to make someone change their thoughts and values to fit in with the group (Keletsositse, 2021).

Peers affect almost all aspects of adolescent lives, from the more trivial, such as taste in music and clothing, to the more serious, such as the use of illicit drugs or engaging in unprotected sex (Castillo, 2022). Studying how peers affect students' motivation is important because it helps understand how students feel and learn in school. When friends influence each other, it can impact how much students enjoy learning and how well they do in school. Figuring out these things can help teachers, parents, and others support students better. By knowing how peer influence affects motivation, we can make schools a friendlier and more helpful place for students, making it easier for them to enjoy learning and do well in their studies.

There are several existing studies on peer influence and students motivation studies (Castillo et al., 2022; Acedillo et al., 2023; Ajibade, 2016; Delay et al., 2016). However, this literature does not delve deeper into the effect of peer influence on students' motivation in a class setting. The dearth of these studies anchors the urgency to conduct this study to address the common problems that the students experience in the context of secondary department of Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. Additionally, the researchers believe that this research is relevant and urgent since it pertains to the students experiences.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study is to determine the effects of peer influence to the motivation of students in the context of Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. This study also sought to answer the specific objectives:

1. To determine the level of peer influence in terms of:
 - 1.1. resistance to peer pressure; and
 - 1.2. peers encouragement
2. To determine the level of student's motivation in terms of:
 - 2.1. intrinsic motivation; and
 - 2.2. extrinsic motivation

3. To establish the significant effect of peer influence to students' motivation in the context of high school students in Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc.

Literature Review

Students' Motivation

Student motivation, also known as learning motivation, is described as "the tendency of a student to find meaningful and useful academic activities and to try to obtain academic benefits from them" (Yilmaz, 2017). Motivation is a fundamental educational variable because it uses previously learned skills, strategies, and behaviors to promote new learning and performance. Without motivation, proper curriculum and good instruction are insufficient to ensure students' success. Motivation can come from a variety of sources for people, particularly for students. The goals a student has for themselves in the classroom can be linked with their level of drive.

Intrinsic Motivation. The study by Adamma et al. (2018), highlights the significance of intrinsic motivation, which is an internal drive that encourages individuals, particularly students, to engage in academic activities because of their genuine enthusiasm for learning and appreciation of the educational process. Intrinsic motivation propels individuals to seek out and embrace new challenges, even without immediate rewards, as they are motivated by a desire for skill development and learning. This intrinsic drive is particularly evident in students who aim to understand and master scientific knowledge and abilities. In contrast, extrinsic motivation, which stems from external rewards or pressures, may have different effects on individuals' behavior.

Extrinsic Motivation. According to Kum (2022), as when a person is motivated by sources other than themselves It is called extrinsic motivation. When someone completes a task or displays a behavior as a result of external influences, such as avoiding punishment or receiving a reward, this is known as extrinsic motivation.

Peer Influence

In the study conducted by Wolf (2015), adolescents typically associate with peers who exhibit similar behaviors, preferences, and attitudes, such as a shared love of music, politics, fashion, or favored pastimes. Two processes have been identified as responsible for this teenage homophily: first, selection factors cause adolescents to initially choose friends with similar attitudes and preferences, and second, over time, they grow increasingly similar to their peers.

Resistance to Peer Pressure. According to DeLay et al. (2016), peers strongly affects in educational choices and whether students make significant investments to improve academic performance or achievement. Constantly following your peers without resistance may lead to poor decision-making, distractions from academic focus, and a potential lack of individuality as a student.

Peers encouragement. According to Spadafora et al (2019), buddies are crucial for teenagers, giving them the support they need to handle tough situations. Having good friends encourages young people to navigate emotional challenges, and research suggests that these friendships can reduce the negative impact of stress on their mental well-being.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the quantitative non-experimental design method of research. The researchers used descriptive-survey research to identify the effects of Peer Influence (IV) on Students' Motivation (DV) among the Students of Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. This is an appropriate method wherein the researchers were able to gather data about the said variables, peer influence, and students' motivation. Creswell argued that when conducting research to larger samples, quantitative research design is the most appropriate one (2018).

Participants

The respondents of the study were the junior and senior high school students currently enrolled in Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. Included in the study are the grade levels 7 to 12. The total population of high school students in the particular school is 181. Using Raosoft calculator, 172 were the total respondents of the study. Excluded in the study are the teachers, students in elementary, and high school students not enrolled in MSSI.

Instruments

The researchers used downloaded modified questionnaires. These instruments were validated by an internal validator and tested through a pilot study. Its Cronbach alpha result yielded at 0.7 which means that the instrument is acceptable and valid for the conduct of the study (Rulona & Bacasmot, 2023). This instrument has two parts, peer influence questionnaire and students' motivation questionnaire.

Procedure

The Nuremberg Code (1947) states that when gathering data from the samples, the research proponents should focus on acquiring voluntary informed consent. The researchers have explained the relevance of the informed consent process to the respondents and explain why they meet the study's inclusion criteria for informants. Furthermore, the researchers gave the respondents adequate time

to read the information contained in the informed consent process and allowed them to ask questions concerning the study's conduct. The researchers honestly valued respect in the process of the conduct of the study and agreement of selected respondents to answer the survey questionnaires in their most convenient and available time.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are integral to this study's conduct. Key elements include ensuring voluntary participation and confidentiality, with participants granted anonymity through the use of numbers or aliases. The informed consent process, aligned with ethical guidelines, prioritizes clarity, respect, and agreement to participate at the respondent's convenience. Additionally, measures are taken to mitigate risks, emphasize mutual benefits, and prevent plagiarism, fabrication, falsification, conflict of interest, and deceit throughout the research process.

Informed Consent Process. Researchers explain the process's relevance, inclusion criteria, and provide adequate time for respondents to understand and ask questions. Respect for respondents and agreement to answer at their convenience was valued aspects of the study's conduct.

Recruitment. Participants were informed about reporting suspicious behavior, and authorization was sought from the High School Coordinator's office and the School Director/Principal's office for a study among student leaders. Endorsement allowed the researchers to disseminate survey questions to student participants.

Risk. No reported risks for respondents were identified, ensuring their safety during data collection. Mutual benefits for both researchers and participants were emphasized, with an assurance that participation should not have a negative impact.

Benefits. Respondents benefit by expressing themselves freely, exercising freedom of expression, and having time for reflection.

Plagiarism. Strict prohibition against copying others' work for inclusion in the research was emphasized to prevent plagiarism.

Fabrication and Falsification. Absolute transparency was encouraged, strongly discourages falsification, warping, or misstating data to ensure the study's quality and accuracy.

Conflict of Interest and Deceit. Researchers were encouraged to avoid biases, prejudices, and be open to new ideas and criticism, promoting an ethical approach to research.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the study that was conducted in the context of Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc.

In Table 1 below, the level of peer influence has weighted mean of 4.23 with the descriptive level of very high. Correspondingly, resistance to peer pressure has the lowest mean value of 4.22 with the descriptive interpretation of very high. All of the indicators got the mean score ranging from 4.20-5.00. This means that the students' motivation is always manifested/observe.

Table 1. *Peer Influence*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Resistance of Peer Pressure	4.22	Very High
Peers Encouragement	4.23	Very High
Overall	4.23	Very High

In Table 2 below, the level of students' motivation has weighted mean of 4.30 with descriptive level of very high. The result shows that extrinsic motivation has the highest mean value of 4.33 which is describe as very high. Meanwhile, intrinsic motivation has the lowest mean value of 4.27 which is also describe as very high. Since 4.30 falls within the range of 4.20-5.00, this means that students' motivation is always manifested/observed.

Table 2. *Students' Motivation*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Intrinsic Motivation	4.27	Very High
Extrinsic Motivation	4.33	Very High
Overall	4.30	Very High

In Table 3 below is the result of the test of the effect of peer influence on students' motivation. The effect is not significant if the f-value is more than 0.05. Reflected on the table below peer influence and students' motivation has an f-value of 0.00. This means that there is a significant relationship between peer influence and students' motivation. In this representation, students' motivation is not significantly affected by peer influence, thus, rejecting the null hypothesis.

Table 3. *Regression Analysis of the Variables*

<i>Pair</i>	<i>Variables</i>	<i>f-value</i>	<i>Decision on Ho</i>
IV and DV	Peer Influence and Students' Motivation	0.00	Rejected

The level of peer influence from the responses is very high. This means that the level of peer influence is always observed in many occasions. All the indicators: resistance to peer pressure; and peers encouragement were described as very high. In Castillo's study in 2022, peers greatly influence social development, as peer interaction gradually increases in adolescence in comparison to childhood.

In examining the motivational system across various prominent conceptual frameworks, it becomes evident that the vast majority, if not all, of its constituent components demonstrate susceptibility to influence through interactions with peers, underscoring the pervasive impact of social dynamics on motivational processes (Kindermann, 2015). Moreover, the very high description of peer influence is confirmed to the findings of Filade et al. (2019), there is significant influence of peer group on academic performance of student. Therefore school administrators and parents/guardians have a role to play in monitoring the types of peer their students and wards move with both in school and outside the home.

The level of students' motivation from the responses is very high. This means that the level of students' motivation is always observed in many occasions. All the indicators: intrinsic motivation; and extrinsic motivation were described as very high. In Yilmaz et al. study in 2017, student motivation, also known as learning motivation, is described as "the tendency of a student to find meaningful and useful academic activities and to try to obtain academic benefits from them.

According to Davidovitch and Dorot (2023), that the processes that lead a specific student to act in a specific way in the classroom are very complex and influenced by interactions between the student's traits, the broad social context, and the specific situation in which the student performs the behavior. Additionally, a study by El-Bialy and Mulay (2015), many studies have suggested that peers have a powerful influence on school adjustment, attitudes, and behaviors. However, there is a paucity of systematic investigations on the relationship between peer influence and student motivation in school engagement.

The relationship between variables test demonstrated a substantial and significant effects of peer influence on students' motivation in the context of a high school. This implied that any adjustment on the level of peer influence has a corresponding effect on the level of students' motivation.

The context of the effects of peer influence on students' motivation is aligned with the findings of Kindermann (2015). He backs up our findings that there is a significant effect between peer influence and students motivation. He stated that peer influence is connected to the students' motivation. The influence of peer groups on the lives of students is an essential component of the social in addition to establishing and preserving a culture distinct from that of the home (Filade et al., 2019).

Conclusions

The level of peer influence from the responses is very high. This means that the level of peer influence is always observed in many occasions. All the indicators: resistance to peer pressure; and peers encouragement were described as very high. Moreover, a very high description of peer influence is also confirmed in the findings of this study.

Additionally, this study found both peer influence and students' motivation to be affecting each other. Therefore, this study concludes that any adjustment made on the peer influence has a significant effect to students' motivation or vice versa. For example, if students are influenced positively through positive interactions by their peers in the school, students say that they become highly and positively motivated. Bad peer influence such as peer pressure would also affect their motivation negatively.

Based on the result of the study, the researchers come up with suggestions and recommendations. In the school, the researchers also recommend that during homeroom time, teachers must include discussing to the students the importance of avoiding peer pressure among each other especially when it comes to academic because it might ruin one's self confidence and motivation to engage in different school activities.

Also, orientations and seminars must be conducted in the school context that requires deeper explanation about the importance of peer influence in the holistic development of the students. This study can help the students have better understanding about how important to stay mentally and physical stable when dealing with academics and that peers can help them achieve it with good guidance.

Parents have a great role in their children's peer interactions. This study may help the parents give constant advice to their children to value friendship. However, parents need to be attentive to the interactions and activities that their children and their peers deal. In connection, teachers, administrators, and stakeholders need to maintain a friendly and conducive environment or classroom to motivate students positively.

Lastly, future research may study the same topics and employ different methods. The researchers suggest that the study should be further extended beyond Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. If this could be done, it would make further revelation on the peer influence on students' motivation. The researchers suggest that this study should be revisited using qualitative context such as interview and observation techniques for data collection. Subjective data would reveal richer contents of the topic. Since this study is limited only among private high school students, future research may include college students and public school students. Other variables such as teachers' competence, class size, gender sensitivity, and the like may be included in the study to determine its effects to students' motivation.

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